

Dual Role of Women and Its Influence on Farmers' Household Income and Consumption Pattern: Study of Informal Women Workers in the District Mandalle, Pangkep, South Sulawesi Province

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Abstract—Today, the number of women who seek additional income to help her husband is increasing. They do that in order to be able to express themselves in the midst of the family and society. Nonetheless, housewives are in charge of managing family's income and prepare food for the family. The objective of this research is 1) to analyze the effect of the dual role of women to household income and 2) to analyze the effect of the dual role to consumption patterns. The study used a qualitative approach, data collection techniques are through observation, interviews, and documentation on farming households. The data was analysed qualitatively descriptively. The results found that: 1) The revenue contribution of women who play double role in the informal sector amounted to 34.07% (less than 50%). 2) The main reason that the respondents worked in the informal sector is to be able to send their children to school (34%) and to improve household economy condition (28%). 3) After earning additional income, respondents said that they can contribute to increase the family's income and to cover the family shortage (82%); 4) Respondents' opinion to changes in food consumption after performing the dual role is the ability to purchase and provide the desired food (44%) and changing patterns of consumption per day (30%).

Keywords—Dual role, the informal sector, consumption patterns, household income.

I. PREFACE

BEING female is not as easy as imagined by a man. Especially, men in Indonesia always relate women with eastern culture as a mother who is elegant, refined, gentle and always close to the family. Since born, women have a nature that distinguishes them from men. Indonesian women are the type of eastern women that exalt their position in the family. Since longtime ago, women pursue their role within the family as a companion to her husband and mother to his children [13]. But, along with the increasing rate of the development and globalization, Indonesian women are now given the opportunity and the same role as men to participate in the national development. The program that counts the role of women in the development is getting more attention, women are given the opportunity to play more roles and enjoy a

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higher education. This fact can be seen in the society where women play an important role in various economic activities [16].

The involvement of women has brought a noticeable impact on women's role in the family. On the one hand, women are working to help their husband in gaining additional income because of the economic needs of the family. On the other hand, they work to be able to express themselves in the society. Family's financial situation affects the tendency of women to participate outside the house, in order to increase the economy of the family [6].

Women's dual role as housewives and workers outside the house (on-farm and off-farm) influences their social behavior in the household. Social behavior that tends to change will affect the structure, function, socio-cultural construction, as well as the management of household consumption patterns of farmers in the countryside.

Women have responsibility in household food security. Their responsibility is from how they process the food until preparing it to the entire family. Mother is the only person who determines the type of food that is served at the dining table. Therefore, women play an important role in the management of household consumption patterns in achieving food security, nutrition and family health. Within this area, a woman takes a decision, such as choosing food, processing it with a healthy way, and selecting the needs of households that are environmentally friendly [14]. Hence, the knowledge of healthy food is necessary to be known by all women, especially women in rural areas.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

This study used a qualitative approach, which aims to reveal the process and interpret the individual behavior that observed holistically [3], [5]. The study design is using *Case Study* model. Case study model with descriptive type, [4], is used to examine the case of the dual role of women [7].

B. Research Location and Research Time

The determination of the location was done purposively in the group of women workers in the informal sector in Mandalle District, Pangkep, South Sulawesi Province. Samples were taken at several villages in the sub district of

Mandalle, namely: 1) Benteng Village is the business location that do fish nuggets and shredded fish. 2) Boddie Village is the business location that sells "dange". 3) Mandalle Village is the business location of cashew nut peeling and seaweed chips making. The study period is ranging from April 2016 to July 2016.

C. Determination of Informant (Data Source)

Respondents in this study consisted of key informants and supporters informants. The key informants are doubled role women, husbands, and children, as a family unit. Reference [8] states that the supporter informants are people that can be used to provide background information on the subject of research. The determination of the informants was done purposively based on the type of work. There are 50 key informants and 3 supporter informants.

D. Data Collection Technique

The data collection in this study used participation observation technique, in-depth interview and documentation.

E. Data Analysis

The data are analysed through descriptive qualitative method by using interactive model as proposed by [7]. The model consists of three main topics, namely data reduction, data presentation and conclusion/verification.

III. RESEARCH RESULT

A. Family Income Management

Family economic stability is largely determined by the ability of the family to manage the sources of income and family finances. In the context of culture (especially Bugis-Makassar culture), "Makkunrai" (female) is the leader who carries out the mandate and credibility to manage sources of income and family finances. This is illustrated by the results of in-depth dialogue with one of the key informants and her husband, like following

KRT said that she tried to manage the family's limited finances as well as possible and trying to scrimp. She limits herself not to buy something that is not very important or dissipate. KRT prefers to have savings or manifest the money in the form gold (interview on May 12, 2016, 10:30 pm).

The results showed that the number of respondents with income between Rp 250,000 - Rp 800,000 is the highest amount with 37 people (74%) and the least is the respondents with total revenues between Rp 1,352,000 - Rp 1,902,000, where only 2 people (10%) out of the total respondents. The smallest (minimum) income is Rp 250,000/month and the highest income (maximum) is Rp 3,000,000/month and the average income of respondents is Rp 890,500/month.

In addition to the income of the wife (respondent), household income is also derived from the husband as the household head. The amount of household income became one of the motivations for women to participate and take part in making a living in order to help the household economy. Their

roles as breadwinner allow them to lighten the burden of their husbands in meeting the financial needs of the household.

Fig. 1 Distribution of Respondents' Income Level

Fig. 2 Distribution of Respondent's Husband Income Level

Sources of household income on female informants are generally from their husbands' income and the income of wives who work in the informal sector.

Based on the data in Fig. 2, it can be seen that 17 (34%) husbands' income level is ranging between Rp 1,502,000 - Rp 2,002,000/month, whereas 2 (4%) husbands have income level ranging between Rp 2,504,000 - Rp 3,000,000/month. The average income of the respondent husband was Rp 1.7227 million/month.

B. Contribution of Respondents' Income to Household Income

The income contribution of respondents to the household income is the contribution of revenue from women who work in the informal sector to the household income. The results analyse the contribution of the 50 respondents. Furthermore, the income contribution of female respondents who work in the informal sector and husband's income to household income can be seen in Table I.

Table I indicates that the contribution of female respondents who work in the informal sector to household income in 2016 amounted to 34.07%. The income contribution of the husband is 65.93%, while there is no income contribution of other

household members. Although there is no contribution of other household members to family income, the level of household income of the respondents still considered sufficient to meet the household needs. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that the contribution of women's dual role on the informal sector to the household income is still relatively small. The percentage of the value of the contribution of respondents earned is less than 50%. Although women's earnings are still relatively small in contributing to the household income, it is valuable to improve family's economic condition and in the fulfillment of various household needs of informal sector players.

TABLE I
 CONTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENT'S INCOME AND HUSBAND'S TO HOUSEHOLD INCOME, IN MANDALLE DISTRICT, 2016

No	Average Income	Value of Contribution	
		(Rp)	(%)
1.	Respondent	890,500	34.07
2.	Husband	1,722,700	65.93
3.	Other household member	0	0
Total of Household Income		2,613,200	100

C. Reasons of Respondents in Working in the Informal Sector

Along with the era of globalization that is being more advance, Indonesian women are now given the opportunity and the same role as men to participate in national development. Economic difficulties forced women from lower economic classes to take part in increasing the family income by working outside the house.

Motivation to work especially for women in middle class is no longer just to help to address the economic needs of the family, but also to use the skills and knowledge that they have acquired and to develop and actualize themselves [9].

TABLE II
 NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS' REASON TO WORK IN THE INFORMAL SECTOR, IN MANDALLE DISTRICT, PANGKEP, 2016

No	Reason of Working in the Informal Sector	Number of Respondents (Person)	Percentage (%)
1.	Increasing family's economy	28	56
2.	Additional income	12	24
3.	Funding social gathering	1	2
4.	Utilizing spare time	1	2
5.	Just for trial	2	4
6.	To send children to school	34	68
7.	Family support	4	8

The data in Table II show that there are many reasons of women to work in the informal sector. The most dominant reason, which shows as many as 34 people (68%) is to send their children to pursue higher education in school, next is improving household economy as many as 28 people (56%), and the percentage of the least, which is only 2%, is to raise funds for social activities and to utilize their spare time. This is supported by the results of in-depth interviews with a respondent named "STR"

"The reason I work in the informal sector which is making shredded fish is because I want to be able to

finance the education of my children up to a higher level to college and beside that to increase household income, so I can help my husband in making a living. I wanted to have a contribution to the household economy and also have savings even though a tiny bit so that if there is an emergency need for family I could handle it (engkato nacede doi ditaro-taro igamissengngi bajasanga di to malasa parellu ki doi dipakei mabbura)" (interview on 17th May 2016 at 11 pm.).

D. Respondents' Thought on Changes in Increasing of Household Income

The main motivation for female worker in general is due to the economic demands of family/as supplement to family incomes. Thus arose the role of women, where beside they have to take care of the household tasks, they also have to work outside the house to gain additional income. Therefore, women should have the ability to adapt well to be able to carry out their dual role [11].

Fig. 3 Percentage of Respondents' Opinion on Income Changes

Based on the data in Fig. 3, it is clearly shown that the changes of household income have brought some positive impacts to the family welfare. The most dominated impact is increased household income and to cover the shortage of family allowances with 42 people (84%), next is the chance to send their children to the college with 34 people (68%) and the least is the ability to pay loans of motorcycle that they have bought with 2 people (4%).

From the result, it can be highlighted about the importance of the role of women in the household economy, and the most important is the involvement of women in income generation has increasing the household income. This is along with the opinion of [10], which says that if household's economic situation is not sufficient anymore, women will go to work for a living to enhance the family income. Although their income is relatively small but that amount still meaningful especially they can contribute something to strengthen the household economy.

E. Household Consumption Pattern

Food is a basic human need. Food types are varying based on the processing methods. In the community, there is an eating habit that exists depending on their culture.

Food consumption is one of the subsystems of food security that is closely related to the level of nutritional status. This is then causing nutrition as an important factor in determining the level of human health and welfare. Nutritional state of a person said to be good if there is a balance of physical and mental development [2].

In the household, women are the key actors in achieving food security for their family. One reason is that food security is part of their reproductive role. The fact that the function of the household as the unit of consumption, developing women's reproductive role to ensure the food security of the family. The data in Table III show the various respondents' opinion to a change in the food consumption of the family after they perform a dual role in the informal sector.

TABLE III
RESPONDENTS' OPINION OF CHANGES IN FAMILY FOOD CONSUMPTION IN MANDALLE DISTRICT, PANGKEP, 2016

No	Opinion	Number of Respondents (Person)	Percentage (%)
1.	To purchase the desired food	22	44
2.	To change food pattern (changes varied menu)	15	30
3.	To consume chicken and meat	10	20
4.	To be able to eat in restaurant	3	6
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data Analysis, 2016.

Table III shows different responses of respondents regarding the changes in household food consumption. A total of 22 people (44%) stated that since having their own income they can buy all kinds of food that they want. 15 people (30%) said that they can alter consumption patterns every day. There are also respondents who stated that they were able to consume chicken and meat at any time not only on special days such as Eidul-Fitr and Eid al-Adha as many as 10 people (20%). The least response with only 3 people said that they could afford to eat at the restaurant.

The results also found that for the provision of family food, the mother is in charge of shopping the groceries and allocating the family's income. Selection of food items in the case studies is more dominantly influenced by the need to fill the stomach, rather than on the selection menu for the nutrient contents. It is in line with [15] which stated that the requirement to eat is more underlying mother's choice to food. Mother prepared food menu and food ingredients as well as select a variety of cuisine but did not list a written menu.

Table IV shows a change in eating frequency of respondents and family members before and after working in the informal economy. One contributing factor is because the respondent has been able to provide breakfast for the family even though the food is very simple such as fried banana, fried sweet potato, stewed sweet potato, and served with tea, coffee, or mineral water. This is in accordance with [12] which stated

that if people get a higher income level, their purchasing power to food will also increase.

TABLE IV
RESPONDENTS AND FAMILY'S EATING FREQUENCY IN MANDALLE DISTRICT, PANGKEP, 2016

No	Situation	Eating Frequency				Total	%
		2 times/day		3 times/day			
		Amount	%	Amount	%		
1.	Before working in the informal sector	30	60	20	40	50	100
2.	After working in the informal sector	11	22	39	78	50	100

Source: Primary Data Analysis, 2016.

TABLE V
TYPES OF FOODS CONSUMED BY FAMILY OF WOMEN WHO WORK IN THE INFORMAL SECTOR IN MANDALLE DISTRICT, PANGKEP, 2016

Types of food	Eating Time					
	Breakfast	%	Lunch	%	Dinner	%
Fried rice	2	4	4	8	-	-
Cakes	31	62	-	-	-	-
Instant noodle	-	-	2	4	-	-
Rice with side dishes	8	16	4	8	-	-
Rice, side dishes and vegetables	9	18	40	80	50	100
Total	50	100	50	100	50	100

Source: Primary Data Analysis, 2016.

Table V indicates that the type of food that is consumed by respondents in the morning is mostly pastries and snacks such as fried banana, fried sweet potato, stewed sweet potato with 31 people (62%). On the other hand, there are 9 people (18%) of respondents who eat rice, side dishes and vegetables for breakfast, then as many as 8 respondents (16%) who consume rice and side dishes without vegetables at breakfast and lastly, there were only 2 respondents (4%) who eat fried rice in the morning.

At lunch, generally respondents with a total of 40 people (80%) consume a full menu of rice, side dishes and vegetables. There are 4 respondents (8%) who consumed fried rice and only 2 respondents (4%) who consume instant noodles as their meals during daytime. Lastly, there are 4 people (8%) who take rice and side dishes for their lunch. For consumption in the evening, all respondents (100%) have the same patterns of consumption, which are rice, side dishes and vegetables. Family consumption pattern is still dominated by rice, vegetables and side dishes (fish) and other non-vegetarian menu.

References [12] and [15] have revealed that women play a role in the household and national food security. Women have the roles in producing, processing and distributing the food at the household level. Mother is the most person in the family who determines the type of food served at the dining table to be eaten by every member of the family, so they often have specific knowledge about the nutritional value and the diversity of food sources. This will contribute to family food security [1].

Based on the data in Table VI, it is clearly shown that the way that respondents serve the food for their families varies depending on the habit at their home. Most of the respondents

with the total of 32 people (64%) serve the food then eat together with the whole family members in the dining table, while there are only 5 respondents (10%) that serve their food in the dining table without eating the food together with their family members.

TABLE VI
THE WAY THAT RESPONDENTS SERVE THE FOOD FOR THE FAMILY IN
MANDALLE DISTRICT, 2016

No	Options	Number of Respondents (Person)	Percentage (%)
1.	Served only	5	10
2.	Served and eating together	32	64
3.	Not served	13	26
Total		50	100

Source: Primary Data Analysis, 2016

Reference [1] said that social aspect, economic and culture in a family have a strong influence on what, when, and how people eat. This is in line with the opinion of [2] that culture affects people in choosing the food, what type of food that should be produced (planted) and consumed, way of processing, preparation and way to serve the food.

In addition to the serving of the food and the consumption pattern, the source of food is also very important. The amount and the diversification of food crops are usually grown from the local area since a long time ago. Moreover, the scarcity of food and working habits of the family also affect the diet. Food sources for daily consumption of the respondents can be seen in Table VII.

TABLE VII
SOURCES OF FOOD PROVIDED BY RESPONDENTS FOR DAILY CONSUMPTION IN
MANDALLE DISTRICT, PANGKEP, 2016

No	Choices	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Buy	50	100
2.	Cultivate on own farm/garden and fishpond	22	44

Source: Data Primary Analysis, 2016.

Table VII proved that all the respondents, which consists of 50 people (100%) obtained food for daily consumption from purchasing it from the traditional markets. In addition to buying, they also usually provide food from the farm/garden and fishpond that they own. There are 22 people (44%) of the total respondents who provide their food not only by purchasing it but also by harvesting it from their own farm/garden and fishpond; such as rice, cassava, bananas and vegetables. In addition, the results also found that mothers prepared food ingredients and select a variety of cuisine, but do not make a written menu, so there are some repetitions of the menu that is consumed by the family every day.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study found: (1) The contribution of women who have a dual role in an informal sector to the overall household income is still relatively small. The percentage of the value of the contribution of respondents earned is less than 50%; (2) The desire and the main motivation of respondents working in

the informal sector is so that their children can have a better formal education to be an independent person in the future (34%) and to help to raise the household economy (28%); 3) Respondents' opinion regarding the increasing household's incomes is that they can have additional income for family and to cover family's financial deficiencies (82%); 4) Respondents' thought on changes in food consumption after performing the dual role is they are able to purchase and provide the desired food (44%) and changing the daily consumption pattern (variation of menu) of (30%);

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Author would like to thank Ditlitabmas and General Director of Higher Education Research and Technology, Indonesia Ministry of National Education on funding competitive research grants Fundamental Fiscal year 2016.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alfiasari. 2007. *Analysis of Poor Household Food Security and the Role of Social Capital* (Case Study on Poor Households in Tanah Sareal District dan Kota Bogor District) Thesis not published, Post Graduate School of IPB: Bogor
- [2] Baliwati, Yayuk Farida dkk. 2004. *Introduction to Food and Nutrition*. Bogor: Penebar Swadaya
- [3] Bogdan, Robert and Steven J. Taylor. *Qualitative Research*. Surabaya: Usaha Nasional; 1993
- [4] Bungin, Burhan. 2008. *Qualitative Research Methods*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada; 2008: 45-48
- [5] Creswell, John. W. *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Traditions*. USA: Sage Publication; 1998
- [6] Ihromi, T. O. 1995. Working Women and the Problems; in Toety H. Noerhadi (ed), *The Dynamics of Indonesian Women*, Jakarta: Center of Women Resources Development.
- [7] Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A. M. *Qualitative Data Analysis*. A Translate of: Rohidi, T.R. (1992). Jakarta: University of Indonesia Press; 1992: 53 – 55
- [8] Moleong, Lexy, J. *Qualitative Research Methods*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya; 2006: 95 - 110
- [9] Nugroho, Riant. *Gender and Gender Mainstreaming Strategy in Indonesia*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar; 2010: 25-26.
- [10] Pudjiwati. *Women's Role in the Development of Rural Communities*, Jakarta: Rajawali; 1987: 54 – 68.
- [11] Saptari, Ratna and Holzner, Brigitte. *Working Women and Social Changes*. Jakarta: Kalyanamitra; 1997; 96 – 108.
- [12] Tobing, Farida Lumban. 2010. *Overview of Family Food Security and Nutritional Status of Mother and Infant in a Food Shortage Area in the District of Tanjung Baringin, Serdang Bedagai*. USU (<http://repository.usu.ac.id/bitstream/123456789/14731/1/10E00493.pdf>)
- [13] UNDP. *The Economic Democracy Financing Human Development in Indonesia. National Human Development Report*. BPS – Statistic Indonesia. BAPPENAS; 2006: 125-126
- [14] Yuliati, Yayuk. *Ecological Changes and Adaptation Strategies of Communities in Tengger Mountain: An Environmental Assessment with Gender Perspective*. PPS UNIBRAW/S3. Brawijaya University; 2008: 94 – 95
- [15] Yuni Puspita. 2015. *The Power of Knowledge of Women About Food Fulfillment in Farmers Family*. (<http://repository.ipb.ac.id/handle/>) accessed on 9th January, 2016.
- [16] Yusuf, Ria Puspa. 2008. *Dynamic Characteristics of Dual Role of Women*. (<http://www/mjlhrkandiria.pdf>). Accessed on 20th December 2010.